

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

SUBJECT-ENVIRONMENTAL APPROACH IN TRANSFORMING THE CONTENT OF THE TUTORING MODEL

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Abstract

In the article, the author argues that the subject-environmental approach plays a significant role in transforming the content of the tutoring model. The author examines the definitions of "educational environment" and "subject agency," acknowledging their integrative nature. According to the author, the subject-environmental approach is effective because it focuses on utilizing the potential of the interaction between the environment and the subject, thereby promoting the development of students' universal competencies.

Keywords: tutoring model, transformation, tutoring activity, tutoring process, educational environment, subject agency.

The subject-environmental approach integrates the provisions of environmental and subjective approaches, expanding the scope of their influence in the tutoring process. Addressing the subject-environmental approach emphasizes the interaction and mutual influence between the environment and the subject. From the perspective of the subject-environmental approach, the environment is not only a means of formation but also a means of personality development. The subject-environmental approach is aimed at studying and utilizing the developmental potential of the interaction between the environment and the subject [14, p. 12].

The concept of the educational environment in pedagogical science is considered from two perspectives: in a broad sense, it is an educational space where pedagogically organized development of personality takes place, as a specially created system of organizing the life of an individual according to pedagogical goals, aimed at shaping their attitude towards the world and people; in a narrow sense, it is a multilevel system of factors (circumstances, conditions, influences, opportunities for personality development) that ensures optimal parameters of educational activities for a particular educational subject in all aspects - goal-oriented, resource-based, content-based, procedural, outcome-based, influencing the formation and functioning of individuals in society, their abilities, needs, interests, and consciousness [4; 12; 15; 16].

Researchers who have conducted a thorough analysis of the concept of "educational environment" provide their generalizations regarding the term and its structural components. Thus, O. Petrenko, summarizing his research on the definition of "educational environment," concludes that the term "educational environment" can be referred to as "the natural or artificially created environment of participants in the educational process in the space of education, which includes the content and means of education aimed at ensuring productive creative activity of the individual, their educa-

tional development, a system of relations between people united by common pedagogical and educational activities" [8, p. 10].

R. Zhoga analyzed the essence of the concept of "educational environment," based on which we can determine that the common characteristics of explaining the term are: a system or set of influences, opportunities, resources, components - specially created or designed; providing or creating opportunities for personality development [3, p. 168]. L. Karpova substantiates the position that the following features are characteristic of the educational environment: integrity, systematicity, unity, variability, structuredness, organization, flexibility, communicativeness, eventfulness, cultural appropriateness, openness, stability, dialogueness, functionality, adaptability, and the ability for self-organization and self-development, and optimally created educational environment is a means of personality development [4, p. 67]. The researcher also notes that in defining the structural components of the educational environment, repetitive elements such as material-technical, psychological-didactic, social, communicative, educational, content-methodological, etc., are quite common.

O. Mezentseva, based on the works of Ukrainian and foreign scholars, has developed a three-level model of the educational environment of a general secondary education institution, consisting of the following components: content-didactic component (educational content; forms and methods of teaching organization; system of assessment of personal development of students; psychological-pedagogical support; connection with pedagogical science); social component (features of the subjects of the educational environment; community values; communication sphere; activity sphere; organizational conditions and management); subject-spatial component (architectural-aesthetic organization of living space; conditions for movement and placement of students; special attributes of the educational process; organization of extracurricular space) [10, p. 112]. O.

Yezhova identifies the main blocks of the educational environment as material-technical, educational, and communicative. Under the material-technical block, the researcher understands the spatial-object component; under the educational block - content, forms, and methods of teaching and upbringing; under the communicative block - relationships between student and pedagogical collectives in general and within each of them individually [2, p. 149].

Based on the study of theoretical scientific-pedagogical developments, we can conclude that the educational environment is interpreted as a social space in which the interaction of its participants takes place; as a set of influences and means of personality development. The tutoring process requires a variable educational environment to focus on the active position of the participants in this process, stimulate initiative, orientation towards the child, individualization, and personalization (which entails subject-subject relations), and provide opportunities for freedom of choice. It is also noteworthy that in modern conditions, flexibility, openness, and mobility are important characteristics of the educational environment.

Let us specify the subject-environmental approach in transforming the content of the tutoring model. It's essential for us to emphasize that the educational environment of a general secondary education institution is a specially organized complex of conditions for the tutoring process, aimed at developing students' universal competencies. The active and full utilization of the opportunities provided by the school's educational environment ensures the successful development of students' personalities. Thus, it is necessary to organize the educational environment in such a way that every student can master it and participate in its development [11, p. 221]. We agree with the opinions of L. Khimchuk and I. Chervinska that the subject-environmental approach contributes to the methodological orientation of tutors towards improving the developmental potential of the interaction between the subject and the environment and characterizes the integral system of actions of the subject in a particular environment, leading to qualitative transformation of this environment through mutual influence [13, p. 50].

The concept of subject agency in the educational process, particularly in tutoring, is defined by researchers as the active, purposeful, initiative, creative, and constructive position of the individual in everyday life [6, p. 53]. A. Boyko notes that "...the recognition of the uniqueness and intrinsic value of each individual, endowed with their unique natural data, subjective social experience, and competencies, capable of initiative, activity, and independence as the subject-possible basis of human existence" lies at the core of subject agency [1, p. 15]. Thus, the emphasis is placed on the awareness of the individual's right to their own opinion, freedom of choice, freedom of action, i.e., self-awareness as an autonomous, independent subject of social action, and readiness to influence social reality in various spheres of public life, being an active participant in transformative actions within it [19, p. 511].

Let us consider the subject approach from the perspective of the development and self-development of the student's personality: the subjective position is the basis for the self-development of the individual, their individuality; the teacher's agency serves as a catalyst for the development of the student's agency; from the perspective of the tutoring process - the development of the student's agency characteristics [5]. Such characteristics may include: persistent internal motivation for development and self-improvement; the presence of value orientations that determine behaviour and are regulated by internal life goals and values; flexibility in designing one's own individual educational trajectory; the ability to regulate one's behaviour in achieving goals and solving tasks; the ability to evaluate one's decisions, actions, analyze them, compare them with one's own plans and the plans of other people; the ability for equal interaction with the surrounding world [7, p. 106].

The agency of an individual is not a constant characteristic but exists under certain conditions, namely within the societal context, which directly determines the possibility of manifesting the agency-related qualities of the individual or agency of the individual during a specific period [17, p. 16]. In the context of tutoring activities, the formation of subject agency among high school students lies predominantly within the school environment. The educational environment of a general secondary education institution represents a unique socio-cultural space where the formation of students' agency occurs. Within the educational environment of the school, social interactions take place, which are modelled within the educational institution and directly influence the formation of students' agency during tutoring activities [17, p. 16].

We agree with the opinions of O. Yakymovych and Y. Ilchshyna that the advantages of the subject-environmental approach in educational practice, particularly in tutoring, include: 1) researching the situation of personality development in the conditions of a specially created environment and studying the issue of their integration; 2) the influence on the student is mostly mediated; 3) the subject-environmental approach allows the student to independently navigate in the accelerated flow of information while ensuring maximum adaptation; 4) this approach, by involving the student as a subject in the educational process and utilizing the entire arsenal of tutoring tools, allows the development of a technology that takes into account the impact on all analyzers, promoting integrity and harmony in influencing the personality [18, p. 353].

Therefore, as a methodological approach, the subject-environmental approach in transforming the content of the tutoring model can be a strategy for addressing issues related to the development of students' universal competencies through the transformation of the educational environment [9, p. 193]. Drawing on the research of Ukrainian scholars [9; 13], we identify the following main principles of the subject-environmental approach: principles of humanism, activity, partnership, cooperation, reflexivity, individualization, dynamism, initiative, responsibility, and lifelong learning.

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